

Room temperature ferromagnetism in transparent and conducting Mn-doped SnO₂ thin films

Sushant Gupta¹, V. Ganesan², N. P. Lalla², Indra Sulania³ and B. Das^{1*}

¹Department of Physics, University of Lucknow, Lucknow-226007, India

²UGC-DAE Consortium for Scientific Research, Indore-452017, India

³Inter University Accelerator Centre (IUAC), New Delhi-110067, India

bdas226010@gmail.com, +91-9415375890

Tin oxide is an attractive material for solar cells and gas sensing applications due to its high optical transparency (above 80% in the visible range of the electromagnetic spectra) and electrical conductivity (carrier concentration of the order of 10^{20} cm⁻³) [1, 2]. Recently there is an increased interest to introduce magnetic functionality in tin oxide semiconductors due to their promising applications in spintronics [3, 4]. The tin oxide semiconductor can be made ferromagnetic by doping with transition-metal (TM) ions. The first report of high Curie temperature ferromagnetism in tin oxide thin films was by Ogale et. al. [5], who reported a

Curie temperature $T_c = 650$ K in pulsed laser deposited rutile (Sn_{1-x}Co_x)O₂ thin films with $x = 5$ -27%, and an amazingly giant magnetic moment of $(7.5+0.5) \mu_B$ per Co ion. The present paper reports the studies on the structural, microstructural, optical and magnetic properties of thin films of Sn_{1-x}Mn_xO₂ with molar ratios of $x = \text{Mn}/(\text{Sn} + \text{Mn}) = 0.000, 0.025, 0.050, 0.075, 0.100, 0.125$ and 0.150 , prepared by spray pyrolysis method. The magnetization (M) as a function of magnetic field showed hysteretic behavior at room temperature. According to the temperature dependence of the magnetization, the Curie temperature (T_c) is higher than 350 K. Ferromagnetic Mn-doped tin oxide thin films exhibited low electrical resistivity and high optical transmittance in the visible region (400-800 nm). The coexistence of ferromagnetism, high visible transparency and high electrical conductivity in the Mn-doped SnO₂ films is expected to be a desirable trait for spintronics devices.

Optical transparency; electrical conductivity; ferromagnetism; Curie temperature (T_c); spintronics.

References

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